

167312_felice_marvella_sucahyo _ 167312_FELICE_MARVELLA_SUCAHYO.pdf

 Quick Submit

 Quick Submit

 LKC

Document Details

Submission ID

trn:oid::1:3604158896

Submission Date

Jun 30, 2026, 6:27 PM GMT+7

Download Date

Jun 30, 2026, 6:51 PM GMT+7

File Name

167312_FELICE_MARVELLA_SUCAHYO.pdf

File Size

548.4 KB

41 Pages

9,963 Words

57,955 Characters

*% detected as AI

AI detection includes the possibility of false positives. Although some text in this submission is likely AI generated, scores below the 20% threshold are not surfaced because they have a higher likelihood of false positives.

Caution: Review required.

It is essential to understand the limitations of AI detection before making decisions about a student's work. We encourage you to learn more about Turnitin's AI detection capabilities before using the tool.

Disclaimer

Our AI writing assessment is designed to help educators identify text that might be prepared by a generative AI tool. Our AI writing assessment may not always be accurate (i.e., our AI models may produce either false positive results or false negative results), so it should not be used as the sole basis for adverse actions against a student. It takes further scrutiny and human judgment in conjunction with an organization's application of its specific academic policies to determine whether any academic misconduct has occurred.

How Generation Z Processes Green Cryptocurrency Investments: CEST and Cognitive Fit

Felice Marvella Suahyo

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2199-3393>

Bina Nusantara University, Indonesia

Muhammad Alif Daffa Ramadhan

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-7817-5330>

Bina Nusantara University, Indonesia

Damar Aji Irawan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1244-2637>

Bina Nusantara University, Indonesia

Author Note

Damar Aji Irawan <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1244-2637>

All authors contributed equally to the research paper. Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Damar Aji Irawan, Bina Nusantara University, Indonesia. Email: damar.irawan@binus.ac.id

Abstract

Generation Z represents 27.94% of Indonesia's population and is a key driver in the capital market, balancing financial pragmatism and sustainability values, particularly in green cryptocurrency investment (Johnston, 2023; Pierre Rainer, 2023; Wood, 2022). This study examines their investment decision-making based on Cognitive-Experiential Self-Theory (CEST) and Cognitive Fit Theory, with Cognitive effort as a mediator, based on a sample of 189 Indonesian Gen Z investors analyzed using PLS-SEM. Results indicate that rational thinking positively significantly influences cognitive effort and investment decisions, while cognitive effort partially mediates this relationship. Among all sub-dimensions, rational favorability emerges as the sole dominant predictor for investment decision in green cryptocurrency, indicating a preference for rational thinking even when individual's ability may be limited, consistent with CEST Theory. The study also show alignment with Cognitive Fit Theory, as decision-making in green cryptocurrency—despite involving emotions—turns out is still treated as a “decision-making” in which needs more of rational analytical lens, where individuals highly rely on structured reasoning and cost–benefit evaluation, not solely on emotions (Hammond & Raiffa, 1998; Moshman, 2004; Posner, 1998; Power et al., 2019). This study is limited by self-reported data, cross-sectional data from Indonesian respondents, restricting generalizability and causal inference, and focusing on intentions rather than actual behavior; future research should adopt longitudinal and cross-regional designs, include additional psychological factors, while fintech platforms and policymakers can improve financial literacy and decision-making through educational tools and decision-support features (KARAKOÇ, 2016).

Keyword

Investment decision in green cryptocurrency, generation z, cognitive effort, rational thinking, experiential thinking, CEST, Cognitive Fit Theory

How Generation Z Processes Green Cryptocurrency Investments: CEST and Cognitive Fit

Introduction

The 2024 Indonesian Gen Z Report shows that Gen Z in Indonesia's population will account for 27.94% of the country's total population, equivalent to 74.94 million people, **it's also considered as dominant population (Ardanto, 2026)**. Of this total population, some of Generation Z have already entered their productive age, while others will enter their productive age in the next few years (Rafsanjani, & Hannany., 2024). Generation Z is not just a passive observer, with this demographic shift making Gen Z an economic actor who has an influence on financial behavior that shapes the financial market in the future.

Alongside this demographic trend, Indonesia's Financial Services Authority (OJK) recorded an increase of 2.04 million in the number of capital market investors, rising from 10.13 million in 2020 to 12.17 million in 2023 (Rafsanjani, & Hannany., 2024). The inclusion of data from OJK is particularly relevant with this study as it focuses on Gen Z investors within the context of Indonesian financial market. In 2023, more than half of these investors (56.43%) were under 30 years old, the majority of whom belong to Gen Z those born between 1997 and 2012 (Suharto, 2025). These young investors engage not only in long-term investment instruments including stocks, bonds, and mutual funds, but also in higher-risk, higher-return assets, including derivatives trading (Yusup & Gunawan, 2024). This pattern indicates that Gen Z investors are increasingly familiar with managing risk–return trade-offs, raising important questions about how financial considerations are balanced with ethical values in their Investment Decisions.

Beyond financial awareness, Gen Z is widely recognized for its strong concern for sustainability and environmental issues. Compared to previous generations, Gen Z demonstrates a stronger orientation toward climate and sustainability challenges, which influences both consumption patterns and investment choices (Malik & Tass, 2025; Sengupta et al., 2024). It is well known that the motivation behind sustainable decision-making is influenced by the important role of emotions (Schneider & Van Der Linden, 2023). Prior studies show that Gen Z's decisions are shaped by ethical considerations, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and technological developments, positioning this generation as a key driver of change in consumer behavior and modern decision-making (Sawicka & Marcinkowska, 2023). However, experiencing pandemics and financial crises has made Gen Z care more about money and financial security (Spohn, 2024). Different past research may also mention "economic motives" instead of "sustainability" for the adoption of green cryptocurrency (Astri et al., 2024), but hasn't specifically examined for Gen Z. Especially with data trend on 2021-2024, showing that the most frequently searched cryptocurrency-related keywords are "trading," "crypto," and "how to trade crypto," concluding least interest in sustainable cryptocurrency (Gunawan & Sharma, 2025). The same thing mentioned also in Meyer et al. (2024) where the conventional unenvironmental-friendly cryptocurrency is still on the lead. According to a survey conducted by Deloitte, half of Gen Z feel financially insecure even though they prioritize a balance between meaning and money in their decisions (Deloitte, 2025). By 2024, the trend toward ESG has declined in recent years. Meanwhile, factors related to return and risk have become the main factors that do not shift market behavior (Gelfand, 2025). For example, the rate of salary growth among Gen Z's is not proportional to the increase in housing prices (Perdamaian & Zhai, 2024).

From this perspective, Gen Z's financial behavior reflects a balance between idealism and pragmatism. According to Johnston (2022), idealism means that education aims to develop the mind,

consciousness, and self-worth so that individuals can develop their potential for freedom. Meanwhile, pragmatism means that education focuses on experiences derived from reality. This means that knowledge is assessed based on how useful it is in everyday life.

The primary question is not whether investors of Generation Z are willing to sacrifice returns to favor the environmentally friendly alternatives, but rather how they process information to make investment decisions prior the execution of the actual investment [not performance] in the context of more environmentally friendly digital currencies, specifically cryptocurrency, considering their reported risk tolerance in pursuing sustainability goals (Wood, 2022). **This paper won't look for the outcomes of the way of thinking as it may changes gradually regarding context of situation** (Honda, H et al., 2020). Instead, it looks to their way of thinking, as these processes shape each decision (Balasubramanian & Mohan, 2011). Previous studies suggest higher financial literacy Gen Z tend to engage in more structured and informed decision-making, integrating analytical evaluation and personal values, while maintaining a lifestyle oriented toward enjoyment and self-fulfillment (Rima Maisaroh, 2025). But, with the emergence of green cryptocurrencies technology, financial instruments designed to support renewable energy and sustainable practices (Peng et al., 2024), the decision-making process becomes increasingly complex. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the underexplained issue of “which factor is more influential in shaping Gen Z’s investment decisions: Rational (analytical) thinking or Experiential (intuitive) feeling”.

Having the understanding of the factor, it would be easier in the future, to know to what extent are Gen Z investors willing to sacrifice potential financial gains in order to prioritize environmentally sustainable alternatives (trade-offs)? Given that cryptocurrency mining and transaction processes are widely known to consume significant amounts of energy. One of them is

Bitcoin is often the subject of discussion involving environmental issues due to its big energy consumption (Çelik & Özırmak, 2025).

Previous research has examined rational and experiential thinking in relation to stock-flow performance, focusing on how it influences individuals' performance in dynamic systems analysis (Hendijani et al., 2021). However, little attention has been given to how these kind of thinking styles influence investment decisions in emerging technologies such as green cryptocurrency (Chatterjee & Chatterjee, 2017). In addition, earlier studies mostly used cognitive reflection as the mediating factor while this study introduces cognitive effort as a mediator, focusing on things such as perception, memory, and judgment (Bačić & Henry, 2022). Therefore, this study expands the literature towards behavioral finance and sustainable digital investment decisions.

By adopting variables derived from underexplored thinking-style theories, CEST and Cognitive Fit, in investment decisions, this study offers a complementary theoretical perspective and **provides further evidence on the investment decision making in green cryptocurrency**. Rather than introducing entirely new constructs, it reframes existing decision processes through cognitive orientations which have received few mentions in investment research. This approach is especially relevant when it comes to Gen Z, whose financial behaviors and attitudes are shaped by increasingly complex and evolving influences (Patil & Gokhale, 2023). Ultimately, this research highlights a demand for broader and more detailed analytical frameworks to better understand how young investors navigate ethical and financial considerations in the context of cryptocurrency investment.

Theoretical Overview

The following section will present a brief overview of the relevant theories used in the research and an explanation of hypothesis development

CEST Theory

Cognitive Experiential Self Theory (CEST) divides the way individuals process information into dual parallel and interactive systems: the rational and experiential systems (Epstein, 2003; Epstein et al., 1996; Idrogo & Yelderman, 2019; Liang et al., 2022; Shiloh et al., 2002; Witteman et al., 2009). The System Rational works on a level of consciousness and is deliberate, analytic, verbal, slow, and relatively free of emotion, relying on abstract reasoning and logical principles, which makes it suitable for complex and dispassionate analysis. This is in contrast to the experiential system, which functions instantly and automatically; this system is intuitive, rapid, comprehensive, nonverbal, associative, and closely linked to emotions and affectively charged past experiences (Epstein et al., 1996; Shiloh et al., 2002). This system represents information through concrete, context-specific examples and is outcome-oriented, serving as the default mode that guides everyday behavior (Epstein et al., 1996; Shiloh et al., 2002). Consequently, behavior, attitudes, and conscious thought are jointly determined by the interaction of these two systems rather than by a single unified process (Frimpong, 2024; Epstein, 2003; Epstein et al., 1996; Idrogo & Yelderman, 2019), either system can be more effective depending on the situation (Epstein, 1994).

The main assumption of CEST is that the experiential system and the rational system operate simultaneously but independently of one another, allowing intuition and analysis to be activated in parallel during decision-making (Baldacchino et al., 2023; Epstein et al., 1996). This is similar to most other dual-processing theory (Okoli & Ogwu, 2024). Repeated experience or proceduralization tends to strengthen ‘experiential processing’, whereas task demands and motivation can shift dominance toward ‘rational analysis’ (Epstein et al., 1996).

CEST further recognizes individual differences in stability in the extent to which people rely on and effectively use the experiential versus rational systems, which can generate variation in judgment and behavior across individuals (Frimpong, 2024; Shiloh et al., 2002). Heuristic processing is viewed as the natural mode of the experiential system and is primarily driven by individual levels of intuitiveness, although rational processing also contributes to final judgments, supporting the notion that behavior emerges from the joint influence of both systems (Epstein et al., 1996; Shiloh et al., 2002). The relative dominance of each system is shaped by situational characteristics, emotional involvement, customary response patterns, and prior experience (Epstein et al., 1996; Liang et al., 2022). Accordingly, in contexts such as entrepreneurship, crowdfunding, and risk perception, individuals simultaneously draw on affect-based intuitive judgments and cognitive analytical evaluations, highlighting the relevance of CEST for explaining decision-making across diverse behavioral domains (Baldacchino et al., 2023; Frimpong, 2024; Liang et al., 2022).

Cognitive Fit Theory

Cognitive fit theory originated from the concept of information processing, which explains that the process of making decisions begins with identifying the problem, information acquisition, and evaluation of alternatives. In this concept, The process of decision-making is not only

determined by general cognitive ability but is also influenced by how individuals process information (Simon & Newell, 1971). This concept was further developed by Vessey (1991) to measure the quality of individuals in making decisions along with how quickly they make decisions based on structured information formats such as numerical and verbal data (Vessey & Galletta, 1991).

Cognitive Fit Theory is a key concept in Cognitive Psychology, alongside Cognitive Load Theory (Möller et al., 2025). It refers not only to decision-making processes based on individual differences in ability, but also to the cognitive effort required to analyze information received when there is a mismatch between the information and the task (Vessey & Galletta, 1991). An individual will immediately create a problem-solving strategy to map the information received without the need to restructure additional information when cognitive fit occurs, so that the cognitive effort produced is lower (Vessey & Galletta, 1991). However, when cognitive fit does not work well, individuals will tend to increase their cognitive effort because they have to restructure the information, which has the potential to reduce the accuracy of decision making (Payne et al., 1993; Vessey & Galletta, 1991).

Cognitive Fit Theory explains that every investment decision is influenced by how an individual adjusts information, task characteristics, and cognitive strategies, with “cognitive effort” lying at the heart of it (Bačić & Henry, 2022). In terms of investment decision-making, differences in suitability and how individuals process information and adjust data will affect the amount of cognitive effort expended. Financial and non-financial data will influence how individuals adjust the way they process this information (Lurie & Mason, 2007; Vessey & Galletta, 1991). When cognitive fit is achieved, cognitive effort will be allocated more efficiently. Similarly, when there is task

mismatch, it will increase cognitive effort in the analysis and evaluation process (Payne et al., 1993). Therefore, cognitive effort can be used as a link between individual characteristics and how an individual makes Investment Decisions. Individual competencies in the form of financial self-awareness, financial self-efficacy, and financial literacy can influence how individuals manage their cognitive effort. Thus, cognitive effort can be the main mediator in determining the quality of rational Investment Decisions (Hirshleifer, 2020; Sweller, 2011). This study updates the cognitive fit, which makes cognitive effort a mediator that explains an individual's competence in managing their cognition to make complex investment decisions

Hypothesis Development

The Effect of Rational–Experiential Thinking Style on Cognitive Effort

Cognitive-Experiential Self-Theory (CEST), a theory proposed by Epstein (1994), which explains that individuals' processes of receiving information pass through two parallel paths, namely the rational system, which goes through an analytical process based on rules and data and is conscious. Then there is the experiential system, which is intuitive, holistic, and based on minimal cognition (Epstein, 1994; Evans & Stanovich, 2013; Evans, 2008). Within the theoretical framework, the rational system was found to be superior to the experiential system in handling abstract and complex cases, since the experiential system tends to make errors based on heuristics and is high risk, even though this system is more efficient when used for daily tasks (Kahneman, 2011; Stanovich & West, 2000). The CEST extension was developed by Epstein and later refined by Pacini and Epstein (1999). Combined with past study structure of Hendijani et al., (2021) of REI-40, it's broken down to rational ability, rational favorability, experiential ability, and experiential favorability. In the context of investing, these four parts play an important role in the Investment

Decision-making process by shaping how individuals allocate their cognitive resources. Rational ability is individual's report on logical and analytical reasoning. Rational favorability is individual's tendency to rely on and enjoyment from logical and analytical reasoning. Experiential ability is individual's report on utilizing feelings and intuitions when making decisions, while experiential favorability is just their reliance and enjoyment of it (Hendijani et al., 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2014).

A rational way of thinking tends to be systematic, whereas an experiential way of thinking is riskier because it relies on intuition, as revealed by previous studies on cognitive psychological behavior (Toplak et al., 2011; Witteman et al., 2009). Therefore, rational dimensions are hypothesized to positively influence cognitive effort as they promote deliberate and analytical processing, while experiential dimensions are hypothesized to negatively influence cognitive effort as they encourage intuitive and affect-driven shortcuts that bypass deep information processing (Evans & Stanovich, 2013; Hendijani et al., 2021).

To explore this further, Rational Thinking, including Rational Ability and Rational Favorability have a positive significant influence on cognitive effort because investment decision-making is driven by analytical thinking skills regarding preferences and systematic abilities (Hendijani et al., 2021; Pacini & Epstein, 1999). Thus, the rational dimension hypothesis has a positive significant influence on cognitive effort (Evans & Stanovich, 2013). Meanwhile, Experiential Thinking, including Experiential Ability and Experiential Favorability are hypothesized to have a negative significant influence on cognitive effort because cognitive involvement may decrease as a result of the preference for intuitive thinking that relies on shortcuts (Kahneman, 2011; Pacini & Epstein, 1999; Stanovich & West, 2000; Witteman et al., 2009).

H1a: Rational ability has a positive significant effect on cognitive effort.

H1b: Rational favorability has a positive significant effect on cognitive effort.

H1c: Rational has a positive significant effect on cognitive effort

H1d: Experiential ability has a negative significant effect on Cognitive effort.

H1e: Experiential favorability has a negative significant effect on cognitive effort.

H1f: Experiential has a negative significant effect on cognitive effort

The Effect of Cognitive Effort on Investment Decision

Cognitive effort is based on how an individual allocates their mental resources to understand and process information in depth, rather than analyzing solely based on heuristics (Kahneman, 2011; Payne et al., 1993). It will tend to increase, depending on uncertainty and complexity, enabling individuals to evaluate the results of their analysis and thereby reduce cognitive bias (Evans & Stanovich, 2013). From research conducted by Hendijani et al. (2021), high cognitive effort positively impacts analytical and logical performance because individuals tend to actively engage their mental resources to ensure accuracy and minimize the occurrence of bias when relying on intuition-based thinking.

The role of cognitive effort becomes particularly significant when applied to the context of investment decision-making, where individuals are confronted with complex, multi-dimensional, and often ambiguous information that demands deliberate cognitive engagement. Investment decision-making itself is a process in which individuals evaluate financial alternatives, weigh potential risks and returns, and ultimately commit to a course of action under conditions of uncertainty (Kahneman, 2011; Payne et al., 1993). This process is inherently susceptible to cognitive biases, as investors frequently rely on mental shortcuts that reduce the depth of information processing, thereby increasing the likelihood of suboptimal decisions (Evans & Stanovich, 2013). In the specific context of Green Cryptocurrency, this challenge is further amplified, as investors must simultaneously navigate financial considerations such as market volatility and risk-return trade-offs, alongside ethical and environmental dimensions tied to ESG principles (Umar et al., 2023). The dual complexity of financial and sustainability evaluation inherent in Green Cryptocurrency investment therefore demands a higher level of cognitive effort, making it a particularly relevant context in which to examine how deliberate information processing shapes investment outcomes.

H2: Cognitive effort has a positive significant effect on investment decision

The Mediating Role of Cognitive Effort

Cognitive effort functions as a key psychological mechanism that transmits the effects of cognitive styles to Investment Decisions, and it's grounded in Cognitive Fit Theory (Bačić & Henry, 2022). Cognitive Fit Theory plays a key role in Cognitive Psychology just as Cognitive Load Theory whereas cognitive load has been part of mediating role in lots of studies (Dwomor & Wiredu, 2021; Möller et al., 2025). Rational cognitive styles enhance individuals' willingness and capacity to engage in effortful processing, which in turn improves decision quality (Fletcher et al., 2011). Conversely, experiential cognitive styles tend to reduce deliberate processing, thereby weakening investment decision outcomes.

Individuals with higher rational cognitive ability possess stronger analytical capacities that facilitate sustained attention to financial information, risk assessment, and evaluation of alternatives. This enhanced cognitive effort reduces reliance on cognitive shortcuts such as anchoring or overconfidence, leading to more evidence-based investment decisions (Evans & Stanovich, 2013; Stanovich & West, 2000).

Similarly, rational favorability reflects an individual's preference for engaging in reflective reasoning. Individuals who enjoy analytical thinking are more likely to voluntarily exert cognitive effort when evaluating investment information, resulting in more systematic and deliberate decision-making (Pacini & Epstein, 1999; Witteman et al., 2009).

In contrast, experiential ability and experiential favorability emphasize intuitive and affect-driven processing. While such processing may increase efficiency, in complex investment settings it often reduces cognitive effort, increasing the likelihood of biased or suboptimal judgments (Kahneman, 2011; Epstein, 1994).

H3a: Cognitive effort mediates the relationship between rational ability and investment decision

H3b: Cognitive effort mediates the relationship between rational favorability and investment decision

H3c: Cognitive effort mediates the relationship between rational and investment decision

H3d: Cognitive effort mediates the relationship between experiential ability and investment decision.

H3e: Cognitive effort mediates the relationship between experiential favorability and investment decision

H3f: Cognitive effort mediates the relationship between experiential and investment decision

The Direct Effect of Rational-Experiential Thinking Style on Investment Decision

Although cognitive effort acts as a mediator between thinking styles and investment decisions, thinking styles can also independently and directly influence investment decision. Dimensions of thinking styles can have a direct influence on investment decision without mediation (cognitive effort). Research conducted by Hendijani (2021) revealed that rational favorability and experiential favorability significantly influences analytical tasks in the process of decision-making. This direct effect means that cognitive resources are not always allocated to decision-making (Pacini & Epstein, 1999; Sladek et al., 2010).

Individuals with high rational ability have internalized a structured analytical framework through education and experience, enabling them to independently assess the financial benefits and sustainability credentials of investment instruments without the need for lengthy deliberation (Stanovich & West, 2000; Toplak et al., 2011). Rational favorability, as a stable dispositional trait, consistently guides individuals toward more systematic investment behavior, as those who prefer a logic-based approach consistently adopt structured evaluative criteria in their financial choices (Cacioppo & Petty, 1982; Witteman et al., 2009). Conversely, high experiential ability and experiential favorability can lead to investment decision that are overly responsive to affective cues and sustainability narratives rather than objective financial assessments, thereby increasing the risk of suboptimal decisions due to behavioral biases including overconfidence and herding behavior (Kahneman, 2011; Hendijani et al., 2021; Shefrin & Statman, 1985).

H4a: Rational ability has a positive significant effect on investment decision

H4b: Rational favorability has a positive significant effect on investment decision

H4c : Rational has a positive significant effect on investment decision

H4d: Experiential ability has a negative significant effect on investment decision

H4e: Experiential favorability has a negative significant effect on investment decision

H4f: Experiential has a negative significant on investment decision

Figure 1

Relationship of rational and experiential thinking, cognitive effort and investment decision in green cryptocurrency

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20822070>

Figure 2

Relationship of rational and experiential thinking subdimensions, cognitive effort and investment decision in green cryptocurrency

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20822070>

Methodology

The study employed a survey method with a cross-sectional approach to examine and provide empirical evidence of the relationships among rational ability, rational favorability, experiential ability,

experiential favorability, cognitive effort, and investment decision. Indicators of rational ability, rational favorability, experiential ability, and experiential favorability is taken from REI-40 (Hendijani et al., 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2014) whilst cognitive effort scale is taken from Bačić & Henry (2018). The investment decision indicators are taken by modified questions (Adil et al., 2022; Al-Tamimi & Anood Bin Kalli, 2009). The research framework is presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Table 1.
Survey Questions

Variables	Questions
Rational Ability	I am very good at solving problems that require careful logical analysis I have a logical mind I'm good at figuring out complicated problems I am much better at figuring things out logically than most people Reasoning things out carefully is one of my strong points I am a very analytical thinker I do reason well under pressure I have no problem in thinking things through clearly I usually have clear, explainable reasons for my decisions Using logic usually works well for me in figuring out problems in my life
Rational Favorability	I like to have to do a lot of thinking I enjoy solving problems that require hard thinking I try to engage in situations that require thinking in depth about something

I enjoy intellectual challenges

I prefer complex to simple problems

Thinking hard and for a long time about something gives me satisfaction

I enjoy thinking in abstract terms

For me, obtaining the correct answer is more important than understanding every step behind it

Thinking is my idea of an enjoyable activity

Learning new ways to think would be very appealing to me

Experiential Ability

Using my “gut feelings” usually works well for me in figuring out problems in my life

I have a very good sense of intuition

I believe in trusting my hunches

I trust my initial feelings when making Investment Decisions

When it comes to Investment Decisions, I can usually rely on my gut feelings

If I rely on my gut feelings, I often make good decisions

I hardly ever go wrong when I listen to my deepest “gut feelings” to find an answer

I suspect my hunches are often accurate

I can usually feel when an Investment Decision is right or wrong, even if I can't explain how I know

My snap judgments are probably as good as most people's

Experiential Favorability

I like to rely on my intuitive impressions

Intuition can be a very useful way to solve problems

I often go by my instincts when deciding on a course of action

I think it is a good idea to rely on one's intuition for important decisions

I like situations in which I have to rely on intuition

I tend to use my heart as a guide for my actions

I think there are times when one should rely on one's intuition

I believe it is important to make important decisions based on rational considerations

I generally depend on my feelings to help me make decisions

I would want to depend on anyone who described himself or herself as intuitive when it comes to Investment Decision

Cognitive Effort	I didn't take a lot of time to choose an investment
	I am careful about which investment I choose
	I thought very hard about which investment to pick
	I put a lot of effort into making this Investment Decision
	I pay much attention while making this investment choice
	I concentrated a lot while making this investment choice
	It was not difficult for me to make this investment choice
Investment Decision in Green Cryptocurrency	The rate of return on my cryptocurrency investment meets my expectations, even the cryptocurrency uses high energy consumption rather than green cryptocurrency

I consider statements from government officials or cryptocurrency project teams about environmental initiatives when deciding to accept cryptocurrency with high energy usage over green cryptocurrency

I feel satisfied with the return on my cryptocurrency investment, even if it is lower due to choosing green crypto rather than cryptocurrency with high energy usage

I consider the past performance of the cryptocurrency and its environmental commitments before accepting a potential trade-off with green cryptocurrency

I consider my feelings toward the cryptocurrency's technology and features, as well as its environmental efforts, when deciding to prioritize green crypto over higher returns from cryptocurrency with high energy usage

This study applied a five-point Likert scale as this study falls in psychometric fields (Mirahmadizadeh et al., 2018) with responses ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) is scored as 5, Agree (A) as 4, Neutral (N) as 3, Disagree (D) as 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) as 1. The scientific community subsequently adopted $p \leq 0.05$ as a conventional threshold for statistical significance (Cowles & Davis, 1982). These values indicate moderate ($f^2 \geq 0.15$) to large ($f^2 \geq 0.35$) effect sizes, according to Lachenbruch & Cohen (1989) guidelines. Accordingly, $f^2 = 0.15$ was applied as the standardized cut-off for a moderate effect size (Selya et al., 2012).

A study involving 199 participants was conducted, these study participants were received from Google Form shared publicly via personal networks and Qusion. From these participants, after being curated, total of 189 respondents will be analyzed. As the minimum criteria of 89 samples after analyzing in G*Power, the sample size has met it. The demographic characteristics can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2.

Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Male	67	35%
Female	122	65%
Current Employment Status		
Self-Employed	11	6%
Employed Full Time	85	45%
Employed Part-Time	39	21%
Unemployed	8	4%
Incapacity of Work (Sickness Benefit)	3	1.5%
Student	42	22%
Others	1	0.5%
Highest Level of Education		
Diploma	5	2%
Under-Graduate	128	68%
Post-Graduate	4	2%
Highschool	52	28%
Income per Month		
IDR 5-15 Million	170	90%
IDR 15-25 Million	11	6%
IDR 25-35 Million	5	3%
>IDR 35 Million	3	1%
Cryptocurrency trading frequency (1-5)		
1 (very rarely)	15	8%
2	12	6%
3	60	32%
4	83	44%
5 (very often)	19	10%

Result & Discussion

Table 3

Path Coefficients: Figure 1 (Rational and Experiential as Composite Variables)

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t(40)</i>
Cognitive Effort → Investment Decision	0.155	0.074	2.114*
Experiential → Cognitive Effort	0.084	0.064	1.263
Experiential → Investment Decision	0.295	0.063	4.499***
Rational → Cognitive Effort	0.475	0.081	5.768***

Rational → Investment Decision 0.36 0.07 5.116***

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Figure 3

Path Coefficient Rational and Experiential thinking, Cognitive Effort and Investment Decision in Green Cryptocurrency

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20822070>

Table 4

Path Coefficient Figure 2.

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t(40)</i>
Cognitive Effort → Investment Decision	0.166	0.075	2.235*
Experiential Ability → Cognitive Effort	-0.013	0.157	0.065
Experiential Ability → Investment Decision	0.186	0.1	1.823
Experiential Favorability → Cognitive Effort	0.088	0.167	0.494
Experiential Ability → Investment Decision	0.081	0.099	0.77
Rational Ability → Cognitive Effort	0.218	0.111	1.952
Rational Ability → Investment Decision	0.11	0.087	1.243
Rational Favorability → Cognitive Effort	0.272	0.12	2.231*
Rational Favorability → Investment Decision	0.298	0.082	3.564***

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Figure 4

Path Coefficient Rational and Experiential thinking subdimensions, Cognitive Effort and Investment Decision in Green Cryptocurrency

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20822070>

The first model showed that rational has a significantly statistical effect on cognitive effort ($\beta = 0.470, p = 0.000$) and investment decision ($\beta = 0.431, p = <.001$). In turn, cognitive effort mediates and positively significantly influences Investment decision ($\beta = 0.156, p = 0.035$). Rational ability showed a marginally positive significant relationship with cognitive effort ($\beta = 0.217, p = 0.051$). Meanwhile, experiential only is significant to investment decision ($\beta = 0.297, p = <.001$), not to cognitive effort ($\beta = 0.081, p = 0.207$), even though both are positive.

The second model indicates that rational favorability has a strongly positive influence on cognitive effort ($\beta = 0.267, p = 0.026$) and investment decision ($\beta = 0.293, p = <.001$). In turn, cognitive effort mediates partially by positively predicting investment decision ($\beta = 0.169, p = 0.025$). Rational ability showed a marginally positive significant relationship with cognitive effort ($\beta = 0.217, p = 0.051$). Meanwhile, experiential ability had only a weak direct effect on investment decision ($\beta = 0.183, p = 0.068$). Experiential favorability was not associated with either of these outcomes.

Figure 3 reveals that Gen Z tends to engage in rational thinking rather than experiential thinking. Meaning, Gen Z is more likely to use analytical reasoning when evaluating and adopting more environmentally friendly cryptocurrencies. Given their stronger tendency towards rationality, Gen Z is more likely to select efficient means to achieve their goals, meaning maximizing the benefit–cost ratio (Posner, 1998). Furthermore, among the rational and experiential dimensions, this analysis in Figure 4. reveals that “rational favorability” is a key predictor when making investment decisions. These findings are also aligned with the study by Hendijani et al. (2021), despite differences in theoretical framework and research context, which reports that rational favorability as the sole dominant variable.

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Table Figure 1

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Rational Ability	189	40.78	5.32	—					
2. Rational Favorability	189	39.49	5.82	.66***	—				
3. Experiential Ability	189	37.17	6.87	.43***	.56***	—			
4. Experiential Favorability	189	37.22	6.69	.34***	.51***	.80***	—		
5. Cognitive Effort	189	28.16	3.81	.43***	.52***	.45***	.45***	—	
6. Investment decision	189	19.24	3.33	.43***	.55***	.50***	.43***	.52***	—

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

small effect = .10, medium (moderate) effect = .30, and large effect = .50

Table 6

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Table Figure 2

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4
1. Rational	189	80.26	10.13	—			
2. Experiential	189	74.39	12.85	.54***	—		
3. Cognitive Effort	189	28.16	3.81	.52***	.47***	—	
4. Investment decision	189	19.23	3.33	.54***	.49***	.52***	—

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

small effect = .10, medium (moderate) effect = .30, and large effect = .50

Table 7

Sample Regression Table Figure 1. with Cognitive Effort as Dependent Variable

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LI	UI	
Rational Ability	.098	.058	-.015	.212	.089
Rational Favorability	.192	.058	.078	.306	.001
Experiential Ability	.028	.059	-.088	.143	.636
Experiential Favorability	.123	.057	.010	.237	.033

Dependent Variable: Cognitive Effort

$p < 0.05$ = Significant

$p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 8

Sample Regression Table Figure 1. with Investment Decision in Green Cryptocurrency

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LI	UI	
Rational Ability	.044	.048	-.050	.138	.358
Rational Favorability	.134	.049	.036	.231	.007
Experiential Ability	.111	.048	.015	.206	.023
Experiential Favorability	-.008	.048	-.103	.087	.867
Cognitive Effort	.243	.061	.123	.363	<.001

Dependent Variable: Investment decision in Green Cryptocurrency

$p < 0.05$ = Significant

$p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 9

Sample Regression Table Figure 2. with Cognitive Effort as Dependent Variable

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LI	UI	
Rational	.141	.027	.089	.194	<.001
Experiential	.081	.021	.039	.122	<.001

Dependent Variable: Cognitive Effort

$p < 0.05$ = Significant

$p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 10

Sample Regression Table Figure 2. Investment Decision in Green Cryptocurrency

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LI	UI	
Rational	.093	.024	.046	.140	<.001
Experiential	.055	.018	.019	.090	.003
Cognitive Effort	.242	.061	.123	.362	<.001

Dependent Variable: Investment decision in Green Cryptocurrency

$p < 0.05$ = Significant

$p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 11

HTMT Figure 1

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.50%	97.50%
E <-> CE	0.306	0.315	0.191	0.449
ID <-> CE	0.484	0.491	0.339	0.646
ID <-> E	0.532	0.536	0.388	0.680

R <-> CE	0.581	0.584	0.420	0.738
R <-> E	0.464	0.468	0.328	0.607
R <-> ID	0.641	0.646	0.516	0.767

HTMT < 0.90 (Ringle et al., 2024)

Table 12

HTMT Figure 2

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.50%	97.50%
EA <-> CE	0.329	0.335	0.188	0.49
EF <-> CE	0.29	0.302	0.186	0.439
EF <-> EA	0.885	0.886	0.816	0.945
ID <-> CE	0.484	0.491	0.339	0.646
ID <-> EA	0.568	0.571	0.422	0.715
ID <-> EF	0.495	0.499	0.349	0.645
RA <-> CE	0.474	0.477	0.297	0.652
RA <-> EA	0.508	0.510	0.359	0.659
RA <-> EF	0.362	0.372	0.235	0.521
RA <-> ID	0.540	0.547	0.401	0.691
RF <-> CE	0.493	0.502	0.339	0.657
RF <-> EA	0.599	0.602	0.473	0.722
RF <-> EF	0.550	0.554	0.442	0.662
RF <-> ID	0.665	0.671	0.552	0.781

HTMT < 0.90 (Ringle et al., 2024)

The sample regression results presented in Tables 9 And Table 10 indicate that the rational and experiential dimensions collectively influence cognitive effort and investment decision in green cryptocurrency, supporting the assumptions of CEST that both systems can operate simultaneously (Epstein, 1994, 2003; Epstein et al., 1996; Idrogo & Yelderman, 2019; Liang et al., 2022; Shiloh et al., 2002). The introduction presents a different result with the Smart PLS 4. This differences in results mainly come from the different validity requirements used by each program. Smart PLS applies stricter criteria, which caused several indicators to be removed during the analysis because they did not meet

the required standards (Ariana et al., 2023). However, since this study primarily employs PLS-SEM as the main analytical approach, the interpretation of the hypotheses follows the SmartPLS results. These finding is further supported by the correlation analysis, where all variables are significant towards cognitive effort and investment decision, but rational exhibits the strongest relationship in Table 6. Similar dominance is found as rational favorability in Table 5 has the closest relationship towards +1 as of the Pearson's correlation coefficient (Mukaka, 2012).

Theoretical and Practical Implications

Epstein's (1994) Cognitive-Experiential Self-Theory (CEST) is supported by this study, as it claims that the *effectiveness of a way of thinking depends on the situation*, and does not imply that rational thinking and experiential are inherently superior, even though they worked in a parallel, which is why both are positively significant towards investment decision in green cryptocurrency. In this research, rational thinking has the dominance, especially rational favorability, has a crucial role in making investment decisions regarding green cryptocurrency, which requires a balance between economic value and sustainability principles in its market. This is the reason why only Rational (Figure 4) and rational favorability (Figure 3) has significant positive effect on cognitive effort.

In line with cognitive fit theory, the evaluation of green cryptocurrency presents a decision-making context that is structured, analytical, and centered on trade-offs (e.g., risk–return and environmental impact), thereby creating a better fit with rational processing (Hammond et al., 1998; Moshman, 2004; Power et al., 2019). This indicates a stronger alignment with rational thinking processes, where individuals tend to “favor” rationality, even if they do not necessarily possess a high level of rational “ability”. This is supported by the findings, showing that only rational favorability has a significant effect and none of the experiential thinking subdimensions are. On the other hand,

cognitive effort **positively significantly** influences investment decision as explained by Cognitive Fit Theory as it posits that cognitive effort is a critical underlying mechanism linking task-representation fit to performance (Bačić & Henry, 2022) even though it is situational, which is why it isn't able to mediate all independent variables (Ntuen, 1999), **only rational from Figure 1 and rational favorability from Figure 2.**

Based on the findings, fintech platforms can provide financial education to users so that they can make sound and informed investment decision (Karakoc M, 2016). This is particularly important given that investors tend to exhibit high rational favorability but relatively low rational ability. **In this context, incorporating logical, data-driven, and verifiable information (e.g risk–return analysis, environmental impact assessments, and other decision-support tools) can help bridge this gap as quality of rationality improved when supported by them (Elgendy, 2022; Jay et al., 2007; Schoenmaker & Schramade, 2023).** Furthermore, policymakers should promote initiatives that combine digital financial literacy with environmental awareness, enabling investors to evaluate both the financial performance and sustainability implications of cryptocurrency investments. This effort can contribute to a more informed and sustainable digital financial ecosystem (Kim et al., 2018).

Conclusion

This study concludes that rational thinking styles particularly rational favorability, strongly dominate positively the decision-making process regarding investments in eco-friendly cryptocurrencies among Generation Z investors. This finding shows that a rational orientation significantly and positively affects both cognitive effort and investment decision. Experiential thinking directly impacts on investment decision but does not significantly influence cognitive effort. Cognitive effort plays a role as a partial mediator connecting rational thinking and investment decision, explaining

the quality of complex decisions driven by analytical processing. Study results show that "rational favorability" has a major positive role in decision-making regarding green cryptocurrency, which can explain that Generation Z can still balance idealism with pragmatism, which prioritizes structured reasoning, even in the context of sustainability-oriented investment decision-making. This finding supports previous research of Asri et al. (2024), suggesting that individuals prioritize economic motives over sustainability when making green cryptocurrency investment decisions. Even when evaluating environmentally friendly investments, they tend to rely on logical reasoning by carefully weighing potential risks and returns rather than depending primarily on intuition or subjective judgments. Thus, this research supports the applicability of CEST and Cognitive Fit Theory in the context of sustainable finance among young investors. Collaboration between policymakers and fintech platforms is needed to create a favorable investment climate by providing financial literacy programs to empower Generation Z to rationally analyze ethical-financial dilemmas. Further research is recommended to utilize longitudinal designs, expand the sample, and add additional theories to further validate each pattern across various contexts and generations.

Limitation

This study has limitations, including bias from self-reported data, which may limit causal inference. Additionally, this study uses a cross-sectional design. Furthermore, means this study cannot be used as a benchmark for Gen Z as a whole, as it only uses Gen Z in Indonesia as a reference. This study cannot be considered an absolute reference due to these limitations, and it does not provide answers regarding actual behavior, but only regarding Gen Z's investment intentions.

Future research could explore in depth the significant influence of rational and rational favorability within the context of differences across regions and generations. To investigate changes in behavior over time, future researchers could employ a longitudinal design. Additionally, incorporating

external moderators such as Self-Determination Theory as a framework to understand external factors is also feasible (Domenico et al., 2022). Furthermore, future research could include a comparative sample across groups to gain a broader understanding of market behaviour.

Open Contribution Statement

All authors are equally contribute to the research paper.

Open Data Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are publicly available on Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.20454294).

AI Declaration

This paper has been checked using Turnitin AI and the result showed that scores are *% detected as AI. AI detection scores below 20%. To reduce the likelihood of misinterpretation, no score or highlights are attributed and are indicated with an asterisk in the report (*%).

Similarity Declaration

This paper has been checked using Turnitin Similarity, and the result showed that the similarity index is below 10%, which is within the acceptable range for academic publications.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20826440>

Corresponding author

Correspondence should be addressed to Damar Aji Irawan:

References

- Adil, M., Singh, Y., & Ansari, Mohd. S. (2022). How financial literacy moderate the association between behaviour biases and investment decision? *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 7(1), 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJAR-09-2020-0086>
- Al-Tamimi, H. A. H., & Anood Bin Kalli, A. (2009). Financial literacy and investment decisions of UAE investors. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 10(5), 500–516. <https://doi.org/10.1108/15265940911001402>
- Ardanto, J. (2026). Struktur Penduduk Indonesia Didominasi Generasi Muda Berdasarkan Data SUPAS 2025. <http://kominfo.kuburaya.go.id/struktur-penduduk-indonesia-didominasi-generasi-muda-berdasarkan-data-supas-2025>
- Ariana, I. K. A., Melinda, R. N., Putri, D. A. P. A. G., & Ariawan, P. (2023). Analisis Pengaruh Perubahan Kontrak (Addendum) Akibat Force Majeure Menggunakan SPSS dan SmartPLS: (Studi Kasus: Proyek BKS-LPD Kabupaten Karangasem) [[Analysis of the impact of contract amendments due to force majeure using SPSS and SmartPLS: A case study of the BKS-LPD Project in Karangasem Regency]. *Jurnal Teknik Sipil*, 19(1), 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jts.v19i1.5256>
- Astri, A. A., Hiererra, S. E., & Lindrianasari. (2024). Driving Forces of Green Cryptocurrency Acceptance: A Systematic Review. *2024 IEEE Conference on Technologies for Sustainability (SusTech)*, 36–42. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SusTech60925.2024.10553579>
- Aziz, F., Rashid, M. A. A., Noor, M., & Othman, A. (2021). Factor Influencing Gen Z Preferred Working Environment in Malaysia. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, Vol. 12(7).

- Bačić, D., & Henry, R. (2022). Advancing our understanding and assessment of cognitive effort in the cognitive fit theory and data visualization context: Eye tracking-based approach. *Decision Support Systems*, 163, 113862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2022.113862>
- Baldacchino, L., Ucbasaran, D., & Cabantous, L. (2023). Linking Experience to Intuition and Cognitive Versatility in New Venture Ideation: A Dual-Process Perspective. *Journal of Management Studies*, 60(5), 1105–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.12794>
- Binus Business School Master Program, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia, Tamara, D., Maharani, A., & Binus Business School Master Program, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia. (2024). How Millennials Make Investment Decisions: Financial Literacy and Financial Behavior. *Economics and Finance in Indonesia*, 70(2), 132–146. <https://doi.org/10.47291/efi.2024.09>
- Brydges, C. R. (2019). Effect Size Guidelines, Sample Size Calculations, and Statistical Power in Gerontology. *Innovation in Aging*, 3(4), igz036. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geroni/igz036>
- Cacioppo, J. T., & Petty, R. E. (1982). The need for cognition. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 42(1), 116–131. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.42.1.116>
- Çelik, A., & Özirmak, M. (2025). Understanding the Association Between Bitcoin Mining and Environmental Sustainability in Light of the Sustainable Development Goals Through the DARDL and KRLS Methods. *Sustainable Development*, 33(5), 6505–6527. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.3471>
- Chatterjee, R., & Chatterjee, R. (2017). An Overview of the Emerging Technology: Blockchain. 2017 3rd International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Networks (CINE), 68–75. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CINE.2017.33>

- Cowles, M., & Davis, C. (1982). On the origins of the .05 level of statistical significance. *American Psychologist*, 37(5), 553–558. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.37.5.553>
- Deloitte. (2025). *Deloitte Global Gen Z & Millennial Survey 2025*.
- Di Domenico, S. I., Ryan, R. M., Bradshaw, E. L., & Duineveld, J. J. (2022). Motivations for personal financial management: A Self-Determination Theory perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 977818. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.977818>
- Dwomor, D., & Wiredu, G. O. (2021). *Smartphone Appropriation and Knowledge Retention in Technology-Mediated Learning*. Conference: African Conference on Information Systems and Technology.
- Elgendy, N. (2022). *Enhancing Collaborative Rationality between Humans and Machines through Data-Driven Decision Evaluation*. BIR Workshops.
- Epstein, S. (1994). Integration of the cognitive and the psychodynamic unconscious. *American Psychologist*, 49(8), 709–724. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.49.8.709>
- Epstein, S., Pacini, R., Denes-Raj, V., & Heier, H. (1996). Individual differences in intuitive–experiential and analytical–rational thinking styles. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71(2), 390–405. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.71.2.390>
- Ergeneli, A., Arı, G. S., & Metin, S. (2007). Psychological empowerment and its relationship to trust in immediate managers. *Journal of Business Research*, 60(1), 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.09.012>
- Evans, J. St. B. T. (2008). Dual-Processing Accounts of Reasoning, Judgment, and Social Cognition. *Annual Review of Psychology*, Vol. 59, January 2008, 59.

- Evans, J. St. B. T., & Stanovich, K. E. (2013). Dual-Process Theories of Higher Cognition: Advancing the Debate. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 8(3), 223–241.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612460685>
- Fletcher, J. M., Marks, A. D. G., & Hine, D. W. (2011). Working memory capacity and cognitive styles in decision-making. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 50(7), 1136–1141.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2011.02.002>
- Frimpong, B. (2024). A Dual-Platform Examination of the Relationship Between CognitiveExperiential Values and Project Success. *Proceedings of the 57th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.
- Frimpong, V. (2024). The Frimpong Case [Graduate Theses and Dissertations, University of Arkansas]. <https://scholarworks.uark.edu/etd/5321>
- Gelfand, A. (2025, January). Young investors' support for ESG dropped dramatically in 2024. In *Stanford Institute for Economic Policy Research (SIEPR)*.
<https://siepr.stanford.edu/news/young-investors-support-esg-dropped-dramatically-2024>
- Gunawan, W., & Sharma, D. (2025). Mapping Public Interest in Cryptocurrency in Indonesia (2021–2024): Analyzing Geographical Disparities and Temporal Trends.
- Hair, J., & Alamer, A. (2022). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) in second language and education research: Guidelines using an applied example. *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*, 1(3), 100027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmal.2022.100027>
- Hammond, J. S., & Raiffa, H. (1998). Even Swaps: A Rational Method for Making Trade-offs. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/1998/03/even-swaps-a-rational-method-for-making-trade-offs>

- Hendijani, R., Ghafourian, F., & Attari, I. (2021). The effect of rational-experiential thinking style on stock-flow performance: The mediating role of cognitive reflection. *Current Psychology*, 42(2), 867–881. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-01459-3>
- Hirshleifer, D. (2020). Presidential Address: Social Transmission Bias in Economics and Finance. *The Journal of Finance*, 75(4), 1779–1831. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jofi.12906>
- Honda, H., Matsuka, T., & Ueda, K. (2020). The effect of context on decisions: Decision by sampling based on probabilistic beliefs. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, vol 42.
- IDN Research Institute. (2024). *Indonesia Gen Z Report 2024*. IDN Research Institute. <https://cdn.idntimes.com/content-documents/indonesia-gen-z-report-2024.pdf>
- Jay, S., Jones, C., Slinn, P., & Wood, C. (2007). Environmental impact assessment: Retrospect and prospect. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 27(4), 287–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2006.12.001>
- Johnston, J. S. (2023). Idealism, Pragmatism, And The Birth of Pragmatist Educational Thought in America. *Encounters in Theory and History of Education*, 23, 259–275. <https://doi.org/10.24908/encounters.v23i0.16274>
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, Fast and Slow*. Penguin Books, London. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00362-013-0533-y>
- Kim, H. B., Choi, S., Kim, B., & Pop-Eleches, C. (2018). The role of education interventions in improving economic rationality. *Science*, 362(6410), 83–86. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aar6987>

- Lachenbruch, P. A., & Cohen, J. (1989). Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences (2nd ed.). *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 84(408), 1096.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2290095>
- Liang, W., Li, Z., Bao, Y., & Xia, B. (2022). Risk Perception of COVID-19 as a Cause of Minority Ethnic Community Tourism Practitioners' Willingness to Change Livelihood Strategies: A Case Study in Gansu Based on Cognitive-Experiential Self-Theory. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(1), 292.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20010292>
- Lurie, N. H., & Mason, C. H. (2007). Visual Representation: Implications for Decision Making. *Journal of Marketing*, 71(1), 160–177. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.71.1.160>
- Malik, I. A., & Tass, M. A. (2025). Driving Environmental Change: The Impact of Social Media on Gen Z's Sustainability Efforts. *South Eastern European Journal of Public Health*, 623–641.
<https://doi.org/10.70135/seejph.vi.3639>
- McLaughlin, J. E., Cox, W. C., Williams, C. R., & Shepherd, G. (2014). Rational and Experiential Decision-Making Preferences of Third-Year Student Pharmacists. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 78(6), 120. <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe786120>
- Meyer, J., Friederich, F., Matute, J., & Schwarz, M. (2024). My money—My problem: How fear-of-missing-out appeals can hinder sustainable investment decisions. *Psychology & Marketing*, 41(11), 2677–2694. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.22077>
- Mirahmadizadeh, A., Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, Delam, H., Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, Seif, M., Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, Bahrami, R., & Shiraz University of Medical Sciences. (2018). Designing, Constructing, and Analyzing Likert Scale

- Data. *Journal of Education and Community Health*, 5(3), 63–72.
<https://doi.org/10.21859/jech.5.3.63>
- Möller, M., Winter, M., & Reichert, M. (2025). Cognitive Factors in Process Model Comprehension—A Systematic Literature Review. *Brain Sciences*, 15(5), 505.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci15050505>
- Moshman, D. (2004a). : From inference to reasoning: The construction of rationality. *Thinking & Reasoning*, 10(2), 221–239. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13546780442000024>
- Moshman, D. (2004b). From inference to reasoning: The construction of rationality. *Thinking & Reasoning*, 10(2), 221–239. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13546780442000024>
- Mukaka, M. M. (2012). Statistics Corner: A guide to appropriate use of Correlation coefficient in medical research. *Malawi Medical Journal*, 24, 69–71.
- Ntuen, C. A. (1999). Examining the Effects of Ecological Models of Situation Displays on Human Cognitive Effort. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 43(3), 293–297. <https://doi.org/10.1177/154193129904300335>
- Okoli, J., & Ogwu, Ibukun. J. (2024). Untangling the Mystery of Intuitive-Analytic Interactions in Crisis Response Operations: A Dual-Process Perspective. *Management Revue*, 35(3), 383–405. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0935-9915-2024-3-383>
- Pacini, R., & Epstein, S. (1999). The relation of rational and experiential information processing styles to personality, basic beliefs, and the ratio-bias phenomenon. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(6), 972–987. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.76.6.972>
- Patil, Y., & Gokhale, R. (2023). Investing in the Age of Millennials and Gen-Z: A Comparative Analysis. *NLDIMSR Innovision Journal of Management Research*, 15–28.
<https://doi.org/10.31794/NLDIMSR.6.2.2022.15-28>

- Peng, P., Liang, F., Fu, Y., Chen, Y., Qiu, L., & Qi, H. (2024). Unraveling the dynamic nexus: Green cryptocurrencies and their role in sustainable market evolution. *Energy*, 313, 133660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.133660>
- Perdamaian, L. G., & Zhai, Z. (John). (2024). Status of Livability in Indonesian Affordable Housing. *Architecture*, 4(2), 281–302. <https://doi.org/10.3390/architecture4020017>
- Posner, R. A. (1998). Rational Choice, Behavioral Economics, and the Law. *Stanford Law Review*, 50(5), 1551. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229305>
- Power, D. J., Cyphert, D., & Roth, R. M. (2019). Analytics, bias, and evidence: The quest for rational decision making. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 28(2), 120–137. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12460125.2019.1623534>
- Rafsanjani, & Hannany. (2024). Swarmed by young investors, capital market's assets still in the hand of veteran. *IDN Finance*.
- Rainer, P. (2023). Sensus BPS: Saat Ini Indonesia Didominasi Oleh Gen Z. *Goodstate*.
- Reddy, A. S., & Deepthi, s. (2024). INVESTMENT DECISION ANALYSIS In CD EQUISEARCH PVT. LTD. *International Journal of Progressive Research in Engineering Management and Science*. <https://doi.org/10.58257/IJPREMS34832>
- Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Becker, J.-M. (2024). *SmartPLS 4*. *SmartPLS 4*. <https://www.smartpls.com>
- Saqib, N., Kapoor, S., Krintz, C., Wolski, R., & Mock, M. (2023). GreenCoin: A Renewable Energy-Aware Cryptocurrency. *2023 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Engineering (IC2E)*, 70–80. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC2E59103.2023.00016>
- Sawicka, J., & Marcinkowska, E. (2023). Environmental CSR and the Purchase Declarations of Generation Z Consumers. *Sustainability*, 15(17), 12759. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151712759>

- Schneider, C. R., & Van Der Linden, S. (2023). An Emotional Road to Sustainability: How Affective Science Can Support pro-Climate Action. *Emotion Review*, 15(4), 284–288.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/17540739231193742>
- Schoenmaker, D., & Schramade, W. (2023). Risk-Return Analysis. In D. Schoenmaker & W. Schramade, *Corporate Finance for Long-Term Value* (pp. 325–366). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35009-2_12
- Selya, A. S., Rose, J. S., Dierker, L. C., Hedeker, D., & Mermelstein, R. J. (2012). A Practical Guide to Calculating Cohen's f^2 , a Measure of Local Effect Size, from PROC MIXED. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00111>
- Sengupta, D., Mathews, M., Bridges, L., D'Costa, R., & Bastian, B. L. (2024). Sustainability Orientation of Generation Z and Its Role in Their Choice of Employer—A Comparative Qualitative Inquiry of India and United States. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(10), 249.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14100249>
- Shefrin, H., & Statman, M. (1985). The Disposition to Sell Winners Too Early and Ride Losers Too Long: Theory and Evidence. *The Journal of Finance*, 40(3), 777–790.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1985.tb05002.x>
- Shiloh, S., Salton, E., & Sharabi, D. (2002). Individual differences in rational and intuitive thinking styles as predictors of heuristic responses and framing effects. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 32(3), 415–429. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(01\)00034-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(01)00034-4)
- Simon, H. A., & Newell, A. (1971). Human problem solving: The state of the theory in 1970. *American Psychologist*, 26(2), 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0030806>

- Sladek, R. M., Bond, M. J., & Phillips, P. A. (2010). Age and gender differences in preferences for rational and experiential thinking. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 49(8), 907–911. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2010.07.028>
- Spohn, D. (2024). Financial Resilience and Innovation among Generation Z in the Face of Economic Adversity. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 1(3), 39–51. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejmeh.2024.1\(3\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejmeh.2024.1(3).04)
- Stanovich, K. E., & West, R. F. (2000). Individual differences in reasoning: Implications for the rationality debate? *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 23(5), 645–665. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00003435>
- Suharto, S. D. (2025, July 9). Artikel Kanwil DJKN Kalimantan Barat. <https://www.djkn.kemenkeu.go.id/kanwil-kalbar/baca-artikel/17731/Mengenal-Generasi-Manusia.html>
- Tejeda, H., Kumar, A., Smyth, P., & Steyvers, M. (2022). AI-Assisted Decision-making: A Cognitive Modeling Approach to Infer Latent Reliance Strategies. *Computational Brain & Behavior*, 5(4), 491–508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-022-00157-y>
- Toplak, M. E., West, R. F., & Stanovich, K. E. (2011). The Cognitive Reflection Test as a predictor of performance on heuristics-and-biases tasks. *Memory & Cognition*, 39(7), 1275–1289. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-011-0104-1>
- Umar, Z., Choi, S.-Y., Teplova, T., & Sokolova, T. (2023). Dynamic spillovers and portfolio implication between green cryptocurrencies and fossil fuels. *PLOS ONE*, 18(8), e0288377. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0288377>
- University of Southern Indiana, Bačić, D., Henry, R. M., & Cleveland State University. (2018). Task-Representation Fit's Impact on Cognitive Effort in the Context of Decision Timeliness and

- Accuracy: A Cognitive Fit Perspective. *AIS Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction*, 164–187. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1thci.00108>
- Vessey, I., & Galletta, D. (1991). Cognitive Fit: An Empirical Study of Information Acquisition. *Information Systems Research*, 2(1), 63–84. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2.1.63>
- Witteman, C., Van Den Bercken, J., Claes, L., & Godoy, A. (2009). Assessing Rational and Intuitive Thinking Styles. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 25(1), 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759.25.1.39>
- Wood, J. (2022, March). Gen Z cares about sustainability more than anyone else – and is starting to make others feel the same. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2022/03/generation-z-sustainability-lifestyle-buying-decisions/>
- Yusup, A. K., & Gunawan, K. (2024). GEN Z INVESTMENT DECISION: ROLE OF FINANCIAL LITERACY, INTEREST AND RISK TOLERANCE USING LOGISTIC REGRESSION. *Ultima Management : Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 16(1), 136–149. <https://doi.org/10.31937/manajemen.v16i1.3667>

Key Terms and Definitions

1. Investment decision in Green Cryptocurrency: to the process of determining when, where, and how to allocate financial resources to environmentally sustainable cryptocurrencies in order to achieve desired financial returns while considering environmental impacts
2. Generation Z: Individuals born between 1997 and 2012
3. Cognitive Effort: Overall amounts of mental resources (e.g. perception, memory, and judgment) required by an individual to do a task

4. Cognitive-Experiential Self-Theory (CEST): Theory of individual's process of thinking through two interacting systems: rational and experiential, with either system becoming more effective depending on the situation
5. Cognitive Fit Theory: A theory suggesting that decision-making becomes more effective when the way information is presented matches how individuals process information.
6. Rational Thinking: Individual's tendency to replace automatic and intuitive responses with conscious and logical reasoning.
7. Experiential Thinking: Individual's tendency to replace conscious and logical reasoning responses with automatic and intuitive.